

The Propagation Property of Micro-vibration Wave at Junction Structures of Composite Honeycomb Plates

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ABSTRACT

The propagation property of micro-vibration wave at the junction structure of honeycomb plates is presents in this paper. A computational method naming energy finite element method (EFEM) is used for obtaining the energy density of structures at a high-frequency range. Generally speaking, complex honeycomb structure should be simplified according to the Hoff theory, the Sandwich theory and the honeycomb plate theory based on the Hamilton dynamic theory. Compared with the conventional finite element method, EFEM uses the averaged energy density as the primary variable to form the governing differential equations. Then, the power transmission coefficients should be confirmed in different junction structures. During the whole analysis process, it is significant to deal with the problem of coupling boundary where the mass block is arranged. From the result of analysis, there is only flexural wave when the linear connection structure is excited and the flexural power is reduced due to the mass block. However, the types of wave in L-junction will change because two plates have been connected orthogonally. Through arranging a mass block at the junction of honeycomb plates, micro-vibration power from the excitation location to the other components reduces outstandingly.

1 FORMULATION OF THE QUESTION

Honeycomb plates have been widely used in the aerospace which has high demands on the material and the structure. For example, the core of solar panels in the satellite is made of the honeycomb plates. Because of the strong application demand of honeycomb plates, the static and dynamic properties have attracted more and more attention for a long time. Micro-vibration with a small amplitude and a wide range of frequency is a kind of vibration which is hard to control in engineering. However, this phenomenon causing a disastrous accident in the satellite structure is ignored most of the time due to the small probability. It is necessary to figure out the law of micro-vibration wave propagation and design optimized structure in order to reduce the impact. In fact, the junction of honeycomb panels in the satellite is very complex, so two simple connection types have been studied in this paper. One is two honeycomb plates connected with 180° that called linear connection as shown in Figure.1, and the other is the L-junction of two honeycomb plates as shown in Figure.2. A mass block is installed between two plates. Firstly, complex honeycomb structure should be simplified according to the Hoff theory, the Sandwich theory and the honeycomb plate theory based on the Hamilton dynamic theory[1]. For obtaining the energy density of structures at a high-frequency range, EFEM[2] is used. Compared with the finite element method and statistical energy analysis, EFEM uses the averaged energy density as the primary variable to form the governing differential equations, which has been proved to be an effective and reliable tool for high frequency vibration analysis. In order to analyze the power transmitted from the excitation plate to the other components at high frequency, it is necessary to calculate the micro-vibration energy transmission coefficients at the connection of two plates[3,4]. Finally, those transmission coefficients are utilized to solve the problem of the energy density throughout the entire system.

Figure.1 linear connection

Figure.2 L-style structure

2 THE PROPAGATION OF MICRO-VIBRATION WAVES

In the calculation, plate 1 is given excitation on the middle and plate 2 are receiving plates in both two cases. Firstly, the transmission coefficients are calculated in the two kinds of connections, as shown in Figure.3. During the range of the low frequency, the sound reduction index should reduce. The data of this frequency is called penetration frequency. However, with the increase of frequency, there is an obstruction frequency, which means that the flexural power excited in plate 1 could not translate into plate 2. Besides the influence of frequency, the size of mass block also has an impact on the sound reduction index. As shown in Figure.3, the penetration frequency and the obstruction frequency could become smaller while the junction is designed with a bigger mass block.

Figure. 3 energy transmission coefficient in the linear connection

Figure. 4 energy transmission coefficient in the L-style connection

3 THE ENERGY DISTRIBUTION OF MICRO-VIBRATION WAVES

To indicate the different values of energy density with the results of EFEM, the simulating diagrams are shown in the Figure 5. In the linear connection structure, the energy density in the middle place of the plate 1 is the maximum and the value of energy density decrease as the distance increases.

Figure.5 (a) the energy density of plate with 20mm mass block
(b) the energy density of plate with 40mm mass block
(c) the energy density of plate excited in 1000Hz frequency
(d) the energy density of plate excited in 4000Hz frequency

In case two, when two plates connected orthogonally are excited, the results are different from the case one. The wave modes should change throughout the entire system and the method will be complex. As shown in Figure.4, there are two kinds of waves coupled with each other. Because the load excited in plate 1 is transverse harmonic force, the main component of waves is flexural wave. Using the power transmission coefficients, the energy density could be calculated in different conditions, as shown in Figure.6 to Figure.9.

Figure.6 the energy density of flexural wave and longitudinal wave in 1000Hz with 30mm mass block

Figure.7 the energy density of flexural wave and longitudinal wave in 3000Hz with 30mm mass block

Figure.8 the energy density of flexural wave and longitudinal wave with 30mm mass block in 500Hz

Figure.9 the energy density of flexural wave and longitudinal wave with 60mm mass block in 500Hz

9 CONCLUSIONS

Energy distribution in the two typical connection structures is researched. To describe it clearly, the energy finite element method is adopted to investigate the structure property. According to the situation of energy distribution, the relationship between the isolation performance and the incident wave frequency or the size of the mass block is analyzed qualitatively. In addition, the isolation performance of the two typical connection structures is evaluated, indicating that the effect of mass block will be reduced when the incident frequency is close to the resonant frequency and the isolation performance will be more effective with bigger mass block.

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